

Supplemental Material for

Mechanical behavior and failure control of anchorage body using constant-resistance large-deformation bolts

Authors:

Pengfei Guo ^{a,c}, Xingyu Zhang ^{b,*}, Zhikang Li ^a, Hongye Zhang ^d, Jinzhu Hu ^a, Fuyang Zhang ^d, Xichun Tian ^a, Danyang Yu ^a, Chuangzhou Wu ^e, Manchao He ^f

Affiliations:

^a School of Civil Engineering, Shaoxing University, Shaoxing, Zhejiang 312000, China

^b Faculty of Geo-Data Science, Geodesy and Environmental Engineering, AGH University of Kraków, Kraków 30-059, Poland

^c School of Mines, China University of Mining and Technology, Xuzhou, Jiangsu 221116, China

^d Zhejiang Ansheng Blasting Engineering Co., Ltd., Shaoxing, Zhejiang 312000, China

^e Institute of Port, Coastal, and Offshore Engineering, Ocean College, Zhejiang University, Zhoushan 316021, China

^f State Key Laboratory of Tunnel Engineering, China University of Mining and Technology (Beijing), Beijing 100083, China

***Correspondence:** zhangxy.leeh@outlook.com (Xingyu Zhang)

S1. Calibration of CRLD bolt resistance and tensile performance

To calibrate the anchoring effect of CRLD bolts on rock masses, a tension-fixing approach was adopted. The mechanical properties of CRLD bolts were assessed through tensile tests using an electronic digital tensile testing machine, as shown in Fig. S1. The measured constant resistance was 345 N, matching the designed value.

Fig. S1 Tensile test of the CRLD bolt.

S2. Full scenarios of specimen failure with different schemes

Fig. S2 presents the complete failure scenarios of CRAB specimens under designed anchorage schemes, illustrating the effects of different bolt quantities, spacings, and inclination angles on crack behaviors and failure modes.

Fig. S2 Failure characteristics of CRABs. (a) Specimens with different anchorage spacings; (b) specimens with different anchorage quantities; and (c) specimens with different anchorage angles.

S3. Temperature responses of all specimens with different schemes

Figs. S3–S5 summarize the temperature responses of all specimens with different supporting conditions during the tests. Compared to the companion specimen, a clear temperature jump is observed throughout the CRAB specimens.

Fig. S3 Temperature variation of the CRAB during tests with different anchorage spacings. (a) 50-mm spacing; (b) 62.5-mm spacing; and (c) 75-mm spacing.

Fig. S4 Temperature variation of the CRAB during tests with different anchorage quantities. (a) No support; (b) one CRLD bolt; (c) two CRLD bolts; and (d) four CRLD bolts.

Fig. S5 Temperature variation of the CRAB during tests with different anchorage angles. (a) 0°; (b) 5°; (b) 10°; and (d) 15°.